

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION A ROOT IN THE MODERN ERA FOR ONLINE EDUCATIONAL WORKSHOP: A SUSTAINABLE APPROACH

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The COVID-19 pandemic led to widespread lockdowns in early 2020, causing many universities to shift to remote learning. This called for Digital revolution, with new strategic plans and values must be redesigned. In digital transformation, many public and private higher education are obstructed: How can they maximize the full potential of digital technology in education? And how can they increase admission rate of the University? This hesitancy place restraint on the transformational power of digital technology and means of private and public institution fall well behind other digital pioneers. This required professional development of faculty members and lecturers to enhance technical knowledge with sharing good practice among all. While some other parts of the world, faculty failed to optimize the use of digital technology and delayed in addressing issues such as online pedagogical shift, online exams, conducting practical labs, online internships and till today they are still exploring solutions to these areas. Online workshops and camps have been organized to sustain in this disruptive technology era to encourage both faculty members and students to join and participate actively.

The crucial goal of universities is to prepare students for successful careers and great citizens, helping to make the sustainable world for brighter future. In the meantime, Institutions should also support faculty by fostering a learning community, providing learning resources and professional development opportunities, and offering required guidance and support. Institutions should encourage academic freedom among students and encourage them to evaluate and access the class and suggest the exceptional work among faculty members. This had contributed to continuous improvement of faculty members as facilitator and create a positive impact on students' learning experience. Faculty members plays a vital role in higher education, regardless of the mode of delivery (online or in person). The value of faculty lies not just in sharing knowledge but their ability to facilitate the growth and progress of their students, as well as generate and co-create new knowledge and solutions that benefit society.

During 2021, Siam University designed the virtual (online) camp by hearing from youth their desire and goals to achieve SDGs. This virtual camp was organized for 3 days using zoom platform under student leadership program: the theme "The New Leadership for Our Sustainable Future" (Figure 1). It was well attended by 40 students; the programme was built around a framework in which students were guided to tackle a challenge related to a Sustainable Development Goal by applying the 4 C's core skills: Collaboration; Communication skill; Critical thinking; and Creativity. This was in partnership with Tokai University in Japan by bringing together students and faculty from eight Asian countries, namely, Bangladesh; P.R. China; Japan; Thailand; Nepal; India; Cambodia; Myanmar to develop the next generation of leaders in tackling sustainability.

Figure 1. Virtual (online) camp

Any Camp despite virtual or onsite it is great platform of listening to youth and learning their skills of disruptive technologies. Technologies is empowering student to make their own decisions through social media, many have become great influencers and youtubers. Higher education institution needs to catch up from theoretical and rote memorization knowledge to experiential learning and problem-solving skills with analytical skills. We have used paperless camp, workshop, conferences, and learning material all available on google platform to utilize with open access anywhere and anytime.

This camp was incredible with enhancing student learning experiences and outcomes where students had to develop self-awareness; with fostering a positive mindset with exemplary lessons from speakers about Corporate Social Responsibility as well as SDGs to be achieved by 2030. This was done by placing learning in a real-world context by creating small groups of five members each with mentors and assigning each Sustainable development goals such as SDG 11 Sustainable cities and communities; or SDG 16: Peace, Justice and Strong institutions and engage them to solve real world problems with solution with encouragement to deeper understand the complexities and possibilities of applying the knowledge that they gain from listening to top-notch speakers during the virtual camp.

The conclusion was driven that SDGs are all interconnected, interrelated and it is not possible to achieve one SDG without the help and partnership of all goals. Sustainability must be adaptable and constantly evolve to ensure always more equity. It is essential that higher education institutions should sustain to fully contribute to sustainable communities and democratic societies. Through this virtual leadership camp till today all are connected through social media and have been in good networking to build and achieve a more sustainable future.

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